

GRAPE TOWN OF KASHMIR, GANDERBAL; STATUS OF AREA AND PRODUCTION OF GRAPES (VITIS VINIFERA)

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Abstract

A Grape is a fruit, botanically a berry, of the deciduous woody vines of the flowering plant genus *Vitis*. The horticulture sector immensely contributes to strengthen the financial condition of the union territory of Jammu and Kashmir, poverty alleviation, employment generation and has become a core sector of the economy of Jammu and Kashmir. It supports around 23 lakh people with direct and indirect work and has the potential for more growth. In view of this, the State Government has declared horticulture a major area and is implementing several measures to enhance it. It is also known as the back bone of the Jammu and Kashmir's economy. The area under the fruit in Jammu and Kashmir has increased from 2.21 lakh hectare in 2001-2002 to 3.33 lakh hectare in 2017-2018 likewise the production has increased from 10.97 Lakh MT's in 2001-2002 to 24.29 Lakh MT's in 2017-2018. Ganderbal, particularly known as The Grape Town of Kashmir is located between 34.23°N and 74.78°E at an average elevation of 1619 metres a.m.s.l. Repora village in Ganderbal district is famous for grapes and one of the Sufi saints of Kashmir Sheikh-ul-Alam has spoken golden words about Repora as "Dachi Repore Nazar Chapoor" means (Repora, the village of grapes and eyes on all sides). The area under grapes in Ganderbal has increased from 84 hectare in 2007-2008 to 192 hectares in 2017-2018, and the production of grapes in the district has increased from 265 MTs in 2007-2008 to 572 MTs in 2017-2018. This study is based on secondary sources of data and an attempt has been made to know the increase in area and production of grapes in district Ganderbal.

Keywords: Grapes, Jammu & Kashmir, Horticulture, Ganderbal, Production, area

Introduction

A Grape is a fruit of the caducous woody vines, a botanical berry, of the flowering plant genus *Vitis*. Grape (*Vitis vinifera*) is a member of the Vitaceae family. Grapes can be consumed as table grapes or utilised as a wine, jam, grape juice, extract of grape seed, grape grapes, raisins, vinegar and grape oil (Angchok, Diwivedi & Ahmad, 2009). Domesticated grapes were cultivated in the Near-East 6000-8000 years ago. Grapes are a fruit that can be crimson, black, dark blue, yellow, green, orange and pink in clusters between 15 and 300. According to the Organization for Food and Agriculture (FAO), 75,866 square kilometres of the planet are grapes. About 71% of the world's grape production is used for wine, 27% for fresh fruits and 2% for dried fruits. Grape was brought to India by the Mughal invasion around 1300 AD. In India, grape production fell following the collapse

of the Mughal dynasty, but was revived by Mohammed-Bin-Tughlak in South India (Aurangabad area of Maharashtra). Grape has been commercially grown in India throughout the last 50 years. It is one of the oldest fruits being grown by man. Grape is one of the most delicious, refreshing and nourishing fruit crops.

Climate

In general, grapes demand a warm and dry climate during their seasons of growth and fruiting. It is successfully cultivated in locations where the temperature range is between 15 and 40 C. During fruit growth and development, high temperatures above 40 C decrease the fruit set and consequently berry size. The bud break is impaired by low temperatures 0 below 15 °C during forward cutting resulting to crop failure. Light influences the fruitfulness of buds. It is grown most well from 200-250m above m.s.l. Area with yearly rainfall that does not exceed 900 mm widely spread all year round is good. However, rainfall during flora and fruit maturation is not beneficial since it leads to the spread of the mildew disease. During vegetative growth and fruiting, high atmospheric moisture is adverse. At high humidity, a vigorous vegetative development of vines impacts the size and quality of the fruit. Similarly, the growth of fungal infections favours high humidity in 30-110 days following forward pruning.

Soil

Varied soils, including sandy loams, sandy clay loams, red and sandy soils, shallow to medium Black soils, and red loams, are suitable for cultivation. The soil should be properly drained, good water capacity, free from hard or impermeable panels in the top 90 cm, with water table at least 6.5 m below them. Grapes can also be effectively cultivated over a broad pH range (4.0-9.5), but pH soils of 6.5-8.0 are considered optimum.

Objectives

The present study has been undertaken with the following objectives

1. To analyse the growth in production and area under grapes in Ganderbal district.
2. To know the role of horticulture department towards grape cultivation in Ganderbal.
3. To identify the existing problems and suggest the suitable measures to overcome the problems.

Materials and Methods

The study is based on secondary data sources. For this study, data from secondary sources were taken and recorded from the Government Official Records, Jammu and Kashmir Economic Survey, Planning and Marketing of the Horticulture Directorate, Magazines, Journals and other agencies related to the State Department of Horticulture. The results were analysed and interpreted via tabulation and a simple percentage procedure. Additional published research papers and state and central government reports were employed to achieve the above mentioned aims.

Study Area

The Ganderbal is a newly formed district in 2007 of the Union Territory of Jammu & Kashmir. It has seven tehsils Tullamulla, waliwar, Lar, Ganderbal, Kangan, Wakura and Gund. The district is located between the 34.23°N and 74.78°E at an average elevation of 1619 metres above sea level, at a distance of 21 kilometres from Srinagar city. The Ganderbal district in Kashmir valley is known for its best quality of grapes. Repora is one of the beautiful villages in district Ganderbal and is situated on Srinagar-Ladakh highway some 6 kms away from district headquarter Ganderbal. Repora is famous for grapes and one of the great Sufi saints of Kashmir, Sheikh-ul-Alam has spoken golden words about Repora as “Dachi Repore Nazar Chapoor” (Repora, the village of grapes and eyes on all sides). The south facing aspect of village makes it feasible for the cultivation of grapes beside being well irrigated and open to maximum possible hours of sunshine. Known for its grapes the village has a mention in the first volume of Tareek-e-Hassan, one of the most reliable historical accounts about Kashmir.

Fig 1. Location Map of Ganderbal District

Results and Discussion

Horticulture is one of Jammu and Kashmir's most dominating sector and backbone with annual revenue of Rs.1200 Crores. It creates direct and indirect jobs for around 23 lakhs and has potential for further. Kashmir valley is obviously popular for its sweet fruits like apple, pears, cherries, walnuts and the tasty grapes. These fruits require normal climatic conditions, moderate rainfall and sunlight and departmental interest. To these tasty fruits have including grapes which is most delicious and is mostly found in the Repora village in central Ganderbal district of Kashmir valley. The best thing about the grapes of Kashmir is that they get ready when there are no grapes in other parts of India. There are several varieties of grapes grown in the district with each having a different taste and color, Hussani green in color, Shahi black in color, Kishmish and Thomson being the others.

The grape growing area in India was 139,000 hectares and 29.20 lakh MT were produced (Dolkar, 2017). Grapes in Jammu and Kashmir are grown in an area of 332 hectares producing 1048 M tonnes and is mainly grown in Repora in Ganderbal district with an area of 192 hectares with an annual crop volume of 606 Mt (2018-2019) and the two main grape varieties are Sahibi and Hussaini, along with other specimens (Anab-e Shahi, Himrod and Thomson seedless) are grown in the Jammu and Kashmir area. Jammu and Kashmir is famed both in India and worldwide for their horticultural products.

Fruit cultivation has been known in Kashmir, since very early times. In Kashmir every aboriginal tree, plant and fruit are known and identified by their local nomenclature like chunt for apple, Tang for pear, Duon for walnut, Fresst for poplar, Aer for plum, Dachh for grapes and so on. Ganderbal district in Kashmir valley is known for its best quality of grapes. Kashmir is well known for some of the best quality apple but not many are aware of the grapes produced in Repora village of district Ganderbal, which according to some experts exceed international standards fixed for the fruit. A great advantage of the Repora grapes is that it is ready when fresh grapes are not available anywhere in the world except Italy.

Horticulture has emerged as an important sector of Jammu and Kashmir it is known as back bone of the economy of Jammu and Kashmir. It employs over 23 lakh people directly and indirectly and has room to develop. Keeping this in mind, the state government has made horticulture a priority and is actively promoting it. The area under the fruit in Jammu and Kashmir has increased from 2.95 lakh hectare in 2007-2008 to 3.33 lakh hectare in 2017-2018 likewise the production has increased from 16.36 Lakh MT's in 2007-2008 to 24.29 Lakh MT's in 2017-2018 (Economic survey Jammu and Kashmir, 2018). The area, production and productivity of different fruits in Jammu and Kashmir of the last three years were tabulated in Table1.

Table 1: Production, area and productivity of all fruits in Jammu and Kashmir UT.

Year	Kind of fruit	Area (Lakh Hect.)	Production (Lakh MTs)	Productivity (Per Hect.)
2015-2016	Fresh	2.41	22.17	9.19
	Dry	0.96	2.76	2.87
	Total	3.37	24.93	7.39
2016-2017	Fresh	2.41	19.59	8.12
	Dry	0.96	2.75	2.86
	Total	3.38	22.34	6.60
2017-2018	Fresh	2.41	21.41	8.88
	Dry	0.91	2.88	3.16
	Total	3.33	24.29	7.29

Fig. 2 Area under grapes in different districts

The above chart reveals that among all the districts of Kashmir valley the highest percentage of grapes grown in Kashmir comes from Ganderbal district, Ganderbal (88%), Baramulla (7.33%), Bandipora (1.83%), Kulgam (1.83%), Kupwara (0.91%). In district Ganderbal grapes are grown in the village of Repora. According to Horticulture department of Jammu and Kashmir the quality of Repora grapes is considered to be best in the world. The international standards of best quality are to have berry size of 4-4.5gms and the grapes from this village have a size of 12.5 grams exceeding the international standards. Prominent commercial varieties grown in the area is the Hussani imported from Iran and Sahibi imported from Hyderabad. There are also Kishmish, Anab-e-Shahi and Ruby varieties. The department of horticulture has now got Thomson seedless variety for raisin making, but lack of local technique in making the raisins is hindering growth in the produce. The Repora grapes fetch a good price in the market. The rate of Sahibi is Rs.200/kg and for Hussani it is Rs.100/kg. The locals have their own technique to preserve the fruit. They keep it in earthen pots and cover them with mud, this way the life of grapes is increased to six months. The villagers attribute the thriving of grapes in area to the blessings of a saint, Mir Syed Shah Sadiq Qalandar (R.A.). The grapes of Repora got attention when someone gifted it to the Rai Bahadur Thakur Janak-the military general of the Maharaja. Impressed by the quality he enquired about the place where the grapes were produced. He purchased most of the fertile area and introduced improved varieties of grapes. Later Janak singh built a Bungalow there which now is also called as Bungli Bagh as the remnants of the building exist there.

The data on the area and annual production of grape in Ganderbal district was tabulated year wise from 2007 to 2018. The data in Table 2 revealed that the area under the grape in 2007 was 84 hectares with a production of about 265 MTs. While as, the present status in 2018 with respect to area and production it was 192 hectares and 572 MTs respectively. It is clear from the table that the area under grapes in the district has doubled in the last 10 years and production has also increased by 2.15 times during the same period. The year wise data of area covered and production of different fruits in Ganderbal district from 2007 to 2018 was tabulated in Table 3.

Table 2: Area, Production and productivity of Grapes from 2017-2018 in Ganderbal.

Year	Area (Hect.)	Production (MTs)	Productivity (Per Hect.)
2007-2008	84	265	3.13
2008-2009	88	278	3.15
2009-2010	91	286	3.14
2010-2011	92	300	3.26
2011-2012	128	231	1.80
2012-2013	139	252	1.81
2013-2014	156	292	1.87
2014-2015	172	330	1.91
2015-2016	188	358	1.90
2016-2017	188	358	1.90
2017-2018	192	572	2.97

Source: (Directorate of Horticulture Kashmir, 2019)

Fig 3: Showing the increasing production of grapes

Table 3: Area and Production of different fruits in District Ganderbal (2017-2018)

Kind of fruit	Area (Hect.)	Production(MTs)
Fresh fruits		
Apple	7111	87576
Pear	385	5023
Apricot	86	721
Peach	190	274
Grapes	192	572
Cherry	1055	3411
Strawberry	6	4
Pomegranate	29	2
Plum	232	1700
Dry fruits		
Walnut	5267	15690
Almond	5	28
Total	14558	115001

Source: (Directorate of Horticulture Kashmir, 2019)

Role of Horticulture department

Traditionally, grape growing was confined to select villages in Kashmir where there was no canopy management idea. Farmers used to make the grape vines grow over unsustainable trees, fence walls and dwelling buildings. Unknown practise was proper training, trimming, shape and canopy care. In the wet season, numerous attachments of fungal infections were particularly widespread in powdery mildew, downy mildew, anthracnose etc. Such unprofessional management also led, due to the insufficient sunlight, in the maturity of most products. In the end, this led to poor quality fruits and poor profits for farmers. Bird damage was also a regular problem, particularly for those bunches of fruit that were exposed at vulnerable vineyards. It was a difficult effort to spray fungicides, thin down from dense vegetative shoots, as summer plant, harvest fruit and manage such vines. This was mainly due to unmanageable vine lengths and uncontrolled offshoot growth. The Department of Horticulture continuously trained the producers on canopy control practises. Some farmers used a technique to raise grapes on wooden structures as a starting point for canopy control.

The J&K state Ganderbal area, particularly Lar block, has been renowned for cultivating Sahibi and Hussaini grapes. The fruit matures in August when grapes are not accessible elsewhere in the country. The grape vines have traditionally been grown on wooden structures. These were usually damaged during heavy snowfall in winter, thus farmers had to re-install these shelters each year. In general, the collapse of these structures owing either to severe snowfall or to a large amount of fruit and vegetative development would damage fruit plants or limit the vineyards' output potential. Moreover, these buildings were not suitable for the proper training and

trimming of grape plants, which hinder the quality of grape output. Heavy disease infection, especially during the rainy season, in these vineyards was a very regular situation.

Intervention in order to modify the scenario and boost grape production, an intervention was made in Lar Block, in particular in Repora and nearby villages in the Ganderbal district, via Rashtriya Vigyan Yojana (RKVY). The grape producers received 50% assistance in the installation of permanent canopy control devices (bower system) in place of traditional wooden structures.

The structures are built under the canopy management plan, which are permanent infrastructures and can even sustain rejuvenated grape vines in the formal training system throughout their lifetime. To date, 414 beneficiaries have been covered under RKVY in order to establish bower systems in Repora and adjacent villages in a cluster way. Around Rs.1 crore has already been paid to help farmers to build an infrastructure worth around Rs.2 crores. The intervention contributed substantially to the improvement of quality grape production. Proper canopy management has dramatically reduced the incidence of disease in grapes and has led to major quality improvements. The RKVY canopy management especially has a clear impact on improving the quality of the products, plant health, saving labour on fruit harvests and other associated tasks necessary to cultivate grapes. The quality impact of the intervention on grapes has been quite successful in persuading farmers to utilise the scientific canopy management technique. One of the most important consequences of this procedure was the ability of farmers' wives to harvest the fruit without any additional support, as canopy management is a tremendous facilitator. This was not practicable before such manufactured bower systems were installed. Ultimately, the quality enhancement led to higher profits for the growers.

As opposed to roughly Rs.10000 per quintal before canopy infrastructure installations, the growers started to collect about Rs.25000 per quintal, thereby registering a 150 percent rise in the production sales of the crop. Apart from improving quality, a further advantage is the decrease of the ongoing costs of rebuilding the wood framework and the frequent damage to the fruit crop. In future years, production and productivity are predicted to grow considerably, since the correct pruning and management of the grapes is facilitated by the installation of the bower system. This will also boost the output of the grapes.

Some of the main problems facing the grape growers are:

- Lack of proper marketing facilities.
- Lack of cold storage/cold chain facilities.
- Lack of processing units/value addition units.
- Low remunerative returns for growers due to higher transportations and higher packing costs.

The growth of horticulture in general and grapes cultivation in particular can be attributed to various initiatives taken by the government

- Introduction of improved varieties mechanization etc.
- Introduction of the new quality, production and productivity technology.

- Create infrastructure through building post-harvest management markets/mandies for inclusive growth.
- Sustainable technology and awareness.
- Publicity and research/extension initiatives, etc.
- Training in the skill of preserving fruit.
- Implementation of plant protection measures.
- Establishment of demonstration plots of grapes.

Conclusion

At present horticulture is one of the major sectors among agriculture and its allied fields that contribute significantly to the Gross State Domestic Production (GSDP). This sector makes a significant contribution to the state's financial sector. The opportunity and possibility to enhance output levels through diversification is greatest in the Union Territory of Jammu and Kashmir, where a 1% shift in area from food grains to non-food grains results in a more than 3% rise in crop output. The Ganderbal district has high potential for cultivation of grapes and increasing the income of local population. But the lack of expert advice and inadequate interest from department sides is denting the production of grapes in the area, so the department should organise awareness camps regarding the high production of grapes.

In order to boost the horticulture crop production state governments should define role clearly and mobilize resource to invest in this sector. Krishi vigyan Kendra and District Horticulture department can play a vital role in providing the planting material to the farmers, provide training's about cultivation technique's and to develop the interest among the orchardist for grape fruit. Agricultural universities should take lead role in providing technical knowledge to the horticulture crops growers in a systematic way, So that farmers are enable to increase the area under fruits and vegetables and achieve the demand of fruits and vegetables. Production of fruits and vegetables can also be increased by scientific production technology. Organic farming also improves the quality of fresh and dry fruits which have high export potential in international market. Quality control laboratories should be established to ensure the exporters the commodities to export that can get international standard in foreign market.

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